

The Preprocessor++ and The New Methodology for Developing New Programming Languages

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Abstract: *The object of interest in this paper is the development of a new methodology for developing new programming languages. The paper focuses on the reasons to propose the methodology: the root cause and the necessity, the rules, the goals and the requirements, the starting point. It examines the implementation: the investigations, development and testing steps, resources and tools, the limitations, workarounds, refinements.*

Keywords: *System programming, Metaprogramming/ Programming languages development, Development methodology, C/C++, Preprocessor/Preprocessor++.*

1. Introduction

The process of developing new programming languages involves heavy tasks such as: program source code lexical, syntactic, semantic analysis; intermediate code optimization, target machine code generation; with testing and optimization efforts, taking three to five times longer than implementation time. Contemporary programming languages such as Rust and Swift are not that different from the C and C++ programming languages. The paper tries to answer the following questions: is it necessary the development of new programming languages to start from scratch, to reach the maturity of the system programming languages C and C++ and to integrate new features such as those of Rust and Swift; or they can be based on and use C and C++, and only integrate new features; can it be achieved systematically with ***simplicity, continuity and efficiency***?

Metaprogramming dates back to first programming languages with Assembly and Lisp macros.

According to the Lilis and Savidis four dimensional taxonomy of metaprogramming languages and systems [1], the proposed Preprocessor++ implementation is (1) *lexical macro system*, operating on sequence of tokens, *pattern-based*, matching and replacing whole new programming language syntactic constructions, but also and *procedural*, because supports algorithmic computations for generating their output, it tries to be *hygienic*, by using scoping, internal naming conventions and rules. On the other hand, the Preprocessor++ operates closely with the C/C++ Preprocessor and performs (2) *preprocessing-time metaprogramming*, it is *source-to-source preprocessor (transpiler)*, translating the new programming language syntax to C/C++ syntax. (3) The Preprocessor++ new programming language definitions and the Preprocessor++ itself are *external* to the subject

program, but the Preprocessor++ new programming language invocations are *embedded* in the subject program, they are *context-unaware*, but try to be *context-aware*, again by using the new programming language syntactic constructions scopes, internal naming conventions and rules, and the supported algorithmic computations for generating their output. (4) The external Preprocessor++ definitions are in *different* language, similar to the C/C++ Preprocessor syntax with regexes, but the embedded Preprocessor++ invocations can be considered as C/C++ *extensions* or *different* new programming language. The Preprocessor++ itself is implemented in C++.

Lilis proposes “Integrated metaprogramming systems: language, tools and practices” [2] - a metaprogramming methodology, involving different metaprogramming models: aspect-oriented programming and multi-stage programming.

The extensive study has shown that there is no analogous preprocessor implementation and usage - the Preprocessor++, whose development is respectively and the new methodology for developing new programming languages.

All the Preprocessor++/ methodology rules, goals and requirements are styled with *italic*. Section 2 represents its toolset order. Section 3 describes the technological challenge, the regexes usage. Section 4 explains the algorithm and the actual implementation. Section 5 - the additional resources and tools used. Section 6 describes the licensing scheme. Section 7 is the conclusion.

2. The toolset

Dennis Ritchie created the C programming language and the UNIX operating system was rewritten in the C programming language.

This defines the system programming domain, as opposite to the application programming domain, it is a software engineering field, in the best scientific sense: computer science, electronics, informatics, *and no place for politicians, economists, lawyers here*.

The C programming language replaces the non-structured assembly languages, that use compare and jump machine instructions for flow control (such as C *if* and *goto*), with no *else*, *switch*, loops and *break/ continue* constructions. The structural and modular programming make UNIX operating system natively portable, maintainable and extendable (on the underlying hardware). The C programming language and the C compilers are evolving by adding new features, so to optimize the compiler generated assembly code is easier than to write optimal assembly code itself.

2.1. The C and The GCC

The current revision of the C standard is C23 [3]. The GNU C Compiler (GCC) has almost full support for it [4]. GCC supports the major hardware architectures and operating systems. It also provides advanced C programming language extensions. The C Preprocessor is developing as well.

2.2. The C++

The current revision of the C++ standard is C++23 [5]. The continuity and compatibility between C and C++ is evolutionary for both system programming languages, that combine optimality and abstractness. *There is no place for opposition between the C and C++ software engineers here.*

2.3. The Preprocessor++

Following the introduced cause-effect relationships, the C programming language can be used as the lowest level programming language in place of the assembly languages for developing new programming languages. The C Preprocessor and the GNU C Compiler can be used for metaprogramming, to define the new programming languages. However, the C Preprocessor has one limitation here - its definitions are identifier-based. The new methodology for developing new programming languages proposes to extend the C Preprocessor, but not to change it and the new extended Preprocessor: PrePreprocessor or Preprocessor++ to be part of the new languages programs build toolchain: as its first and last phase.

This is the root cause and the necessity to propose the methodology.

The Preprocessor++ parameterizes via a definitions file (pppdefs.h) and operates closely with the Preprocessor via a definitions file (pppextensions.h(pp)) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The new languages programs build toolchain

3. The technological challenge

The computer science in a discipline such as “Automata, Languages, Computation”, a part of the discrete mathematics is too abstract and too theoretical. Because of that, more practical investigation is necessary: with the C programming language as the lowest level programming language, the C Preprocessor and the GNU C Compiler, ***the Regular expressions (regex-es) are exploited to their limits.*** This is the main goal of the methodology.

Fig. 2. Chomsky hierarchy refinement

The Chomsky formal language hierarchy has been refined and every high-level programming language is a context-free language (CFL) defined by a context-free grammar (CFG) [6][7] (Fig. 2). The Backus-Naur form (BNF) is foundational CFG for defining the programming languages syntax [8]. However, the BNF is more complex than the Regular expressions and one can compare it with the Prolog logic programming language. On the other hand, the Regular expressions are evolving by adding even irregular extensions.

The Regular expressions library (ECMAScript syntax) [9][10], supported since C++11 standard, the C++ programming language and the GNU C++ Compiler are used for the Preprocessor++ development. *There is no place for “non-system”, “non-native/virtual” or “garbage collecting” technologies here.*

4. The Preprocessor++ implementation

The development environment is set up with Qt Creator 14.0.2 (Community), Qt 6.8.0 llvm-mingw 64-bit and LLVM-MinGW 17.0.6 64-bit for C++.

When the Preprocessor++ operates as first phase of the new language programs build process, the first step is to parse the new language definitions from the pppdefs.h file. Then, starting from a file system directory as a root directory (the new language programs project directory), it searches the directories tree

recursively for the new language source files, including the `pppextensions.h(pp)` file. If the Preprocessor++ finds the inclusion, it copies the new language source file with the extension “.ppp”. Next, it applies the new language definitions from `pppdefs.h` to the original new language source file.

When the Preprocessor++ operates as last phase of the new language programs build process, starting from a file system directory as a root directory (the new language programs project directory), it searches the directories tree recursively for the new language source files with the extension “.ppp” and restores the original new language source files from them.

The Preprocessor++ parses the `pppdefs.h` file line by line for each new language definition and stores the definition in a vector of tuples of strings. Each tuple contains human readable search and replace patterns, and regex search and replace patterns.

The Preprocessor++ applies the new language definitions from the vector of tuples of strings to the original new language source files.

It uses for itself and requires for the new programming languages the Allman (Pascal) indentation style with four spaces indentation size (the best indentation style, according to the author of this paper) and its development started with:

- Syntax disparity fixes: the C syntax languages (C++, C#, Java) declare the variables by placing the type in the left side, but in C/C++ the type array is separated by the variable, by placing the brackets ([]) in the right side (`int iArr[]` instead of `int[] iArr`). This syntax disparity is fixed with the search and replace definitions in the `pppdefs.h` file:

```
#define "T[] t" "T t[]" /* "(\w+)(\[.*\]) (\w+)" : "$1 $3$2" */
#define "T[][] t" "T t[][]" /* "(\w+)(\[.*\][.*\]) (\w+)" : "$1 $3$2" */
#define "T[][][] t" "T t[][][]" /* "(\w+)(\[.*\][.*\][.*\]) (\w+)" : "$1 $3$2" */
#define "T*[] t" "T* t[]" /* "(\w+)(\[.*\]) (\w+)" : "$1 $3$2" */
```

No or any character, except line terminators [10], can be used inside the brackets ([5], [n], [n + 1], [sizeof(n)], [const 5], etc.). *The general requirement is to use regex groups (()) for each significant object in the search string.*

- Operator definitions: C and even C++ (compared to Swift) can not define new operators (Swift can define infix, prefix, postfix operators with precedence and associativity [11]). New operators can be defined by using parentheses for precedence and associativity:

```
#define "operator+/-" "operator_tolerance" /* "(operator)(\x2B\x2F\x2D)" :
"operator_tolerance" */
#define "t1 +/- t2" "operator_tolerance(t1, t2)" /* "\(((.+)) (\x2B\x2F\x2D)
\((.+))\)" : "operator_tolerance($1, $3)" */
```

Regex groups (()) are used for the operator +/- (tolerance) and operands (((5 +/- (1)), (((((4 + 2) + 1)) +/- ((1 + (2 + 4))))), etc.). The expression calculation intermediate results usage improves the code readability and debugging.

The operator +/- is defined as:

```
typedef struct range
{
    double min;
    double max;
}
range;

range operator+/(double const value, double const percent)
{
    range result;

    double d = value * (percent / 100);
    result.min = value - d; result.max = value + d;

    return result;
}
```

- Boundary checks: the pppdefs.h file provides search and replace definitions for array `size()` and array `at(i)`. The C++ programming language concepts are followed:

```
#define "t.at(i)" "at(t, i)" /* "(\\w+)\\. (at)\\(([^()]+)\\)" : "at($1, $3)" */
#define "t.size()" "size(t)" /* "(\\w+)\\. (size)\\(\\)" : "size($1)" */
```

For these definitions the Preprocessor++ operates closely with the Preprocessor via the pppextensions.h file. The `at(t, i)` definition uses a GNU C Compiler extension to C programming language syntax - a statement expression [12]. The statement expression checks if `i` is greater or equal to the array size and if so, `i` changes to array size minus one. The `size(t)` definition is generic:

```
#define at(t, i) (t)[({unsigned _i = (i); _i >= size((t)) ? size((t)) - 1 : _i;})]
#define size(t) _Generic((t), char*: strlen((char const*)(t)), char const*:
strlen((char const*)(t)), default: (sizeof((t)) / sizeof(*(t))))
```

The regex patterns “.” for operator definitions and “[^()]+” for boundary checks can be refined with a regex pattern for expression with nested parentheses. However, with each level of nesting the regex pattern is getting bigger, this is the iterative way (some regex libraries provide also the recursive way, e.g. the Boost C++ library):

Table 1. Regular expressions matching five levels of nested parentheses

Regex	Nesting
<code>\((([^\)]*)\))</code>	1
<code>\(((?:[^\)]*\([^\)]*\))*\))</code>	2

<code>\(((?:[^\(\)]*(?:[^\(\)]*\([^\(\)]*\))*)*)\)</code>	3
<code>\(((?:[^\(\)]*(?:[^\(\)]*\([^\(\)]*\([^\(\)]*\))*)*)\)</code>	4
<code>\(((?:[^\(\)]*(?:[^\(\)]*\([^\(\)]*\([^\(\)]*\([^\(\)]*\))*)*)\)</code>	5

For test, when the regular expression matching five levels of nested parentheses is used to search the three levels of nested parentheses string “(cc(cc(cc)cc(cc)cc)cc(cc(cc)cc(cc)cc)cc)” then the matched string is “cc(cc(cc)cc(cc)cc)cc(cc(cc)cc(cc)cc)cc”.

- Extending types with *methods* and type *optional*: the analogy is Swift *extensions* [13] and Rust *trait* implementations [14]. The C++ programming language concept for *optional* is followed. The Preprocessor is used only and no further explanations are necessary (see Appendix A).

The new programming languages control flow constructions and essential features are implemented, by using the conceptual algorithm design presented in Fig. 3 and explained below.

Fig. 3. The Preprocessor++ conceptual algorithm design

When the Preprocessor++ applies the new language definitions from the vector of tuples of strings to the original new language source files:

1. the source file content (*fcontent*) is copied;
2. *regex_search* is called for the copied *fcontent* with the given definition and on match the match position is stored, and the necessary changes inside the match are made: variable or code indentation replacement for the control flow constructions or whole match replacement for the essential features;
3. the match at the stored position inside the original *fcontent* is replaced with the changed match;
- 1-3 steps are repeated for all matches with equal level of nesting.
4. *regex_replace* is called for the whole original *fcontent* with the given definition;

1-4 steps are repeated five times for five levels of nesting for the control flow constructions.

4 step only is executed for the simple definitions, such as above, and the RAI and Workarounds definitions explained below.

The Preprocessor++ implemented the new programming languages control flow constructions:

- *if-else, switch, while* loop by extending the C syntax with control variable definition, by analogy to the *for* loop. *The C++ programming language concepts are followed.* The `pppdefs.h` file provides search and replace definitions for them (see Bitbucket: <https://bitbucket.org/cobatasoftware/preprocessor/src/main/>).

Generally, the new language source file is searched to match with:

```
if(T t = ti; t)
{
    ...
}
else
{
    ...
}
/* or */
switch(T t = ti; t)
{
    ...
}
/* or */
while(T t = ti; t)
{
    ...
}
```

And the match is replaced with:

```
{
    T t = ti;

    if(t)
    {
        ...
    }
    else
    {
        ...
    }
}
/* or */
```

```

switch(t)
{
    ...
}
/* or */
while(t)
{
    ...
}
}

```

The Allman (Pascal) indentation style with four spaces indentation size is required for and is integrated in the new programming languages syntax, similar to Python and its indentation style and size [15]. This improves the code readability and also overrides the necessity of Regular expressions matching levels of nested braces (see Table 1), by using regexes with irregular extension, namely the backreference `\int [10]` (“\1”, reusing the already matched indentation size).

- *switch case* hashing: by implementing hashing the switch cases can not be only integers, but also doubles and even strings. For this feature the Preprocessor++ replaces actually only strings with their hash, using a simple hashing function and operates closely with the Preprocessor via the `pppextensions.h(pp)` file, using generic hash function (`pppextensions.h`) or using hash function overloading (`pppextensions.hpp`), for the switch argument. The limitation here is that the doubles and the strings have to be *literal values*. This limitation could be solved by evolving the *constexpr* feature in the C and C++ programming languages (see Appendix B1).

- *range-for* loops: by using the C *for* loop syntax are implemented range-for loop with closed interval (`{1 .. 5}`), range-for loop with in place defined array (`{1, 2, 3, 4, 5}`) and range-for loop with already defined array (`iArr`), similar to the C++ programming language range-for loops, but all loops are able to traverse the array both ascending and descending, and also with a step greater than one or even with step returned by a function generator. The Preprocessor++ uses the so called, by the author of this paper, *pre-known-naming* in straight direction - the developer names the objects, the Preprocessor++ uses the names. The `pppdefs.h` file provides search and replace definitions for the range-for loops (see Bitbucket: <https://bitbucket.org/cobatasoftware/preprocessor/src/main/>).

For example, generally, the new language source file is searched to match with:

```

for(int i <- {e0 .. ei}; generator(i!))
/* or */
for(int i <- {e0 .. ei}; step)
/* or */
for(int i <- {e0 .. ei})
/* or */
for(int i -> {e0 .. ei}; generator(i!))

```

```

/* or */
for(int i -> {e0 .. ei}; step)
/* or */
for(int i -> {e0 .. ei})

```

And the match is replaced with:

```

for(int i = ei; i >= e0; i = generator(i))
/* or */
for(int i = ei; i >= e0; i -= step)
/* or */
for(int i = ei; i >= e0; --i)
/* or */
for(int i = e0; i <= ei; i = generator(i))
/* or */
for(int i = e0; i <= ei; i += step)
/* or */
for(int i = e0; i <= ei; ++i)

```

The implemented range-for loops allow nesting and by using the C *for* loop syntax is fixed the inability with the C++ range-for loop with the brace-enclosed initializer list of pointer to chars (*char**), for which iterators are not defined, to be able to traverse the pointer to chars (*char**) (see Appendix B2).

The Preprocessor++ implemented the new programming languages essential features:

- Lambdas: by using local C *structs* and a GNU C Compiler extension to C programming language syntax - nested functions [16] are implemented lambda expressions/ functions. When the lambda function captures variable by value or by reference from the environment then the defined local C *struct* contains the corresponding member variable with respective value or pointer type, and becomes initialized with the captured variable value. The C *struct* contains as first member the function pointer *operator_function* with first parameter *this*, and become initialized with the lambda function itself. The lambda function can be recursive, and in this case must be named and be captured itself. The anonymous lambda implementation is not completed, named lambda and *pre-known-naming* in straight direction (by naming lambda, starting with “_”) could be used as workaround. The Preprocessor++ operates closely with the Preprocessor via the *ppextensions.h* file, by using *pre-known-naming* in reverse direction - the Preprocessor++ names the objects, the developer uses the names (the Preprocessor++ names the lambda struct type, concatenating “_lambda_” with the lambda name):

```

#define _lambda_(type, ...) {type ## __operator_function, ## __VA_ARGS__}
#define _lambda(l) l.operator_function
#define lambda(l, ...) l.operator_function(&l, ## __VA_ARGS__)

```

The C++ programming language concept for lambda expressions/functions is followed. The pppdefs.h file provides search definition for lambdas (see Bitbucket: <https://bitbucket.org/cobatasoftware/preprocessor/src/main/>).

For example, generally, the new language source file is searched to match with:

```
auto factorial = [&factorial](int i) -> int
{
    return i <= 1 ? 1 : i * factorial(i - 1);
};

printf("%d\n", factorial(5));
```

And the match is replaced with:

```
typedef struct _lambda_factorial_lambda_factorial;
struct _lambda_factorial
{
    int (*operator_function)(_lambda_factorial* this, int i);
};
int _lambda_factorial__operator_function(_lambda_factorial* this, int i)
{
    return i <= 1 ? 1 : i * this->operator_function(this, i - 1);
}
_lambda_factorial factorial = {_lambda_factorial__operator_function};
#undef factorial
#define factorial(...) factorial.operator_function(&factorial, __VA_ARGS__)

printf("%d\n", factorial(5));
```

• RAI: by using the GNU C Compiler common variable attribute *cleanup(cleanup_function)* [17] is implemented the basic Resource Acquisition Is Initialization concept, by analogy to the C++ smart pointers, *unique_ptr*. The pppdefs.h file provides the search and replace definition:

```
#define "unique_ptr<T> ptr" "T* unique_ptr(ptr)" /* "(unique_ptr)<(.)>
(\w+)" : "$2* unique_ptr($3)" */
```

For this definition the Preprocessor++ operates closely with the Preprocessor via the pppextensions.h file. The *_free(ptr)* function is called on *ptr* variable definition scope exit:

```
#define unique_ptr(ptr) ptr __attribute__((cleanup(_free)))
```

- Workarounds: the search and replace definition in the pppdefs.h file fixes a GNU C Compiler warning, caused by the use of `__typeof__`("one", "two", "three", "four", "five") macro, by replacing it with the type `char*`:

```
#define "__typeof__(s0, si)" "char*" /* "__typeof__"((\x22.*\x22))" :
"char*" */
```

5. Resources and tools

In addition to the development environment set up in 4, for development and testing of the Preprocessor++ and respectively the new methodology for developing new programming languages are used also a few online resources and tools:

- ideone.com: with GCC 8.3 C/C++ are used for fast code validation.
- cppinsights.io: expanding C++ code is used for the investigations, development and testing.
- godbolt.org: with X86-64 GCC 13.3 C/C++ are used for the investigations, development and testing, the new programming languages are validated with these compilers.

6. The Preprocessor++ licensing

The COBATA Preprocessor++ or the Preprocessor++: its sources, binaries and documentation, is uploaded for free and open source usage in Bitbucket: <https://bitbucket.org/cobatasoftware/preprocessor/src/main/>. **It uses FreeBSD style header (licensing) with an additional clause to do not use it for AI (machine learning, etc.), with a violation penalty.**

7. Conclusion

The Preprocessor++ internal initial release date is 26.11.2024. The time past till now is around seven months. The C++11 standard, with the essential C++ programming language features, is more than seven years after the previous C++03 standard [5]. The Rust initial release year is 2012. The Swift initial release year is 2014.

The duration of development (around seven months/ one developer - the author of this paper), the quantity of the developed control flow constructions and essential features, the quality of the code for the Preprocessor++ and the new programming languages denote, that the proposed methodology for developing new programming languages is promising, with its *simplicity, continuity and efficiency*. It uses the C programming language as the lowest level programming language, the C Preprocessor and the GNU C Compiler for metaprogramming, the C++

programming language for the Preprocessor++ and *the Regular expressions (regexes) exploited to their limits*.

The new methodology for developing new programming languages steps essentially are:

1. Follow the rules, goals and requirements in italic;
2. Use the toolset;
3. Write a good new programming language definition with regex in `pppdefs.h`;
4. Connect the definition with the C/C++ Preprocessor via `pppextensions.h(pp)`;
5. Write a good algorithm, corresponding to the defined new programming language invocation in `apply_pppdefs` in `main.cpp`;
6. Test the feature in `_main.c(pp)`, by using resources and tools.

These investigations and implementations can chart new paths for developing the toolkit used: to evolve the C/C++ `constexpr` feature, to evolve the regex library.

Finally, not for the first time, the author of this paper, while developing software tools, has recognized technological and scientific abstractions that miss and subsequently eliminate new capabilities and optimizations that facilitate software development.

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Appendix A

pppextensions.h:

```
#define nullopt NULL /*nullptr*/
typedef struct _optint _optint;
struct _optint
{
    int __i;
    int* __nullopt;

    int* (*value)(_optint*);
    _optint* (*operator_sharp)(_optint*);
    int (*has_value)(_optint*);
    void (*reset)(_optint*);
} intopt;
int* _optint__value(_optint* this) {return this->__nullopt = &this->__i;}
_optint* _optint__operator_sharp(_optint* this) {this->__i += 2; this->__nullopt = &this->__i; return this;}
int _optint__has_value(_optint* this) {return this->__nullopt ? 1 : 0;}
void _optint__reset(_optint* this) {this->__nullopt = nullopt;}
#define _optint(oi) {(#oi == "nullopt") ? 0 : (intptr_t)(oi), (#oi == "nullopt") ? nullopt : (int*)&intopt, _optint__value, _optint__operator_sharp, _optint__has_value, _optint__reset}
```

_main.c:

```
#define optint _optint

optint k = optint(nullopt /*0*/);

if(k.has_value(&k))
{
    printf("optint is not null: ");
    printf("%d\n", *k.value(&k));
}
else
```

```

    {
        printf("optint is null\n");
    }
    *k.value(&k) = 5;
    if(k.has_value(&k))
    {
        printf("optint is not null: ");
        printf("%d, ", *k.value(&k));
        printf("%d, ", k.operator_sharp(&k)->__i);
        printf("%d\n", *k.value(&k));
    }
    k.reset(&k);
    if(!k.has_value(&k))
    {
        printf("optint is null\n");
    }

    #undef optint

```

output:

```

optint is null
optint is not null: 5, 7, 7
optint is null

```

Appendix B1

pppextensions.hpp:

```
#include <cstdio>
```

```

constexpr long _hash(char const* s)
{
    long result = 0;
    unsigned i = 0;

    result += "" + 25;
    for(; s[i] != '\0'; ++i)
    {
        result += (i + 2) * s[i] + 25;
    }
    result += (i + 2) * "" + 25;

    return result;
}

```

```

}
constexpr long _hash(double const d)
{
    long result = 0;
    char s[41] = {0};

    sprintf(s, "%g", d);
    for(unsigned i = 0; s[i] != '\0'; ++i)
    {
        result += (i + 1) * s[i] + 25;
    }

    return result;
}
constexpr long _hash(long const i) {return i;}
#define switch(t) switch(_hash((t)))

```

proposal.cpp:

```

#include <iostream>

int main()
{
    constexpr char s[] = "test1";

    switch(s)
    {
        /* Will be applied by the Preprocessor++ */
        case _hash(s):
            std::cout << "test1" << std::endl;
            break;
        /* Will be applied by the Preprocessor++ */
        case _hash("test2"):
            std::cout << "test2" << std::endl;
            break;
        default:
            std::cout << "default" << std::endl;
            break;
    }

    return 0;
}

```

output:

test1

Appendix B2

pppextensions.hpp:

```
#include <cstring>
```

```
unsigned size(char const* s)
{
    return strlen(s);
}
```

_main.cpp:

```
#include <iostream>
```

```
int main()
{
    for(auto& l1 : {"one", "two", "three", "four", "five"})
    {
        std::cout << l1 << ", ";
        /*
        for(auto l2 : l1) // error: 'begin'/'end' was not declared in this scope;
        {
            std::cout << l2 << ", ";
        }
        */
        {
            unsigned l1Size = size(l1);

            for(unsigned l2 = 0; l2 < l1Size; ++l2)
            {
                std::cout << l1[l2] << ", ";
            }
        }
    }

    return 0;
}
```

output:

one, o, n, e, two, t, w, o, three, t, h, r, e, e, four, f, o, u, r, five, f, i, v, e,